

Accelerating FAIR Morphological Data Curation with an AI-Empowered Tool

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Curation of morphological datasets, especially those derived from paleontological studies is often a slow, manual process prone to formatting inconsistencies and typographical errors. These issues present major barriers to achieving compliance with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles and reduce the utility of such datasets in large-scale evolutionary and taxonomic research. To address this, we developed an AI-assisted curation pipeline for Morphobank, a collaborative, open-access repository for morphological phylogenetic matrices. This tool automates the extraction, standardization, and integration of morphological character names and states into NEXUS files from published literature. The system utilizes PymuPDF, a tool to make structured text extractions and pre-processing of PDF documents easier. It then removes extraneous content such as references, figures, and parts of the paper that aren't the character list. It then employs Gemini, a large language model, to identify and generate structured morphological character data. These outputs are formatted into a JSON schema and reintegrated into incomplete NEXUS files, improving completeness and dataset interoperability. This approach has been deployed in a large-scale data migration project transferring over 300 matrices from the Paleobiology Database (PBDB) to MorphoBank, significantly reducing manual workload while maintaining high accuracy in character-state extraction. By automating key components of the curation workflow, our AI-based system enhances data quality, accelerates repository integration, and enables broader reuse of legacy phylogenetic datasets. This work demonstrates the potential of AI to support sustainable and scalable data curation practices across paleontology and systematics, paving the way for more reproducible and accessible evolutionary research.

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